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humidity was negatively correlated with outcrossing ($r = -0.47$) and seed yield ($r = -0.5$). The study indicates that seed production can be taken up in areas of artificial irrigation with tube wells or bore wells during summer months (April and May) without hindering the normal crop season.

The outcrossing potential in CMS lines, however, was higher in semiarid zones such as Warangal (43.9%) and Palem (40.2%) than in a humid zone such as Maruteru (19.4%) in Andhra Pradesh. This may be due to the relatively higher humidity (80-90%) and low wind velocity

(mean 1.54 m s^{-1}) prevailing at ARS, Maruteru. Seed production of hybrid rice may thus be more efficient and economical in semiarid zones of the country.

Association between simple sequence repeat (SSR) marker diversity, pedigree record, quantitative trait variation, and hybrid performance in rice

W. Xu, IRRI and Plant Breeding and Biotechnology Division (PBBD), Philippine Rice Research Institute (PhilRice), Nueva Ecija; S.S. Virmani, IRRI; J.E. Hernandez, Department of Agronomy, University of the Philippines Los Baños; Z.K. Li, IRRI; and E.D. Redoña, PBBD, PhilRice, Philippines E-mail: s.s.virmani@cgiar.org

Knowledge of genetic diversity among prospective parental lines is important for the success of a hybrid breeding program. Genetic diversity is usually measured using pedigree information, plant phenotypic data, and molecular markers. In this study, we determined the relationship between various genetic diversity measures and hybrid performance in rice.

The materials used in this study were 37 maintainer and 44 restorer lines of the WA-CMS (wild abortive-cytoplasmic male sterile) system, which represented germplasm of different origins (IRRI, Philippines, and China) used in our tropical hybrid rice breeding program. The pedigrees of these parental lines could be traced back to ultimate ancestors that had no known pedigree information based on published pedigree records (IRRI 1985, 1995) and PhilRice technical notes. Of these lines, 10 maintainer and 18 restorer lines were randomly selected to produce 34 F_1 hybrids in 1997. The hybrids and their parents were evaluated at three field locations in the Philippines from the 1997 dry season to 1998 dry season.

Coefficients of coancestry were calculated for the parental lines using the pedigree information. D^2 estimates were

derived using data on 11 quantitative characters: days to flowering, flag leaf length and width (cm), plant height (cm), number of productive tillers, panicle length (cm), 100-grain weight (g), grain yield per plant (g), grain length and width (mm), and panicle weight (g). SSR assays with 37 primer pairs were made at PhilRice's Genetic Laboratory. Nei and Li (1979) coefficients were then derived. Correlation analysis between various diversity measures and hybrid performance or midparent heterosis on six measured traits (plant height, grain yield, total plant weight, 100-grain weight, grain length and width) was performed.

In the analysis of variance across three locations, significant to highly significant differences were observed for all quantitative traits under investigation, except for flag leaf width. The mean number of alleles per SSR locus was 4.24 ± 1.71 , ranging from 2 to 9. There was one locus where more than 5 alleles were resolved.

There was no or poor correlation between different measurements of diversity and the pedigree records for both B and R lines (Table 1). These results suggested that the methods for measuring

genetic diversity are not consistently associated with each other. This confirms previous reports in durum wheat (Autrique et al 1996) and barley (Shut et al 1997).

No correlation was observed between the diversity measures based on all SSR markers and F_1 performance or midparent heterosis for all quantitative traits measured (Table 2), indicating that molecular diversity in a random set of SSR markers is not useful in predicting midparent heterosis. Prediction power should be improved if selected markers are linked to quantitative trait loci affecting heterosis. Genetic diversity measured by the pedigree-based coefficient of coancestry was significantly correlated with the F_1 mean performance but not with midparent heterosis for highly heritable traits, including 100-grain weight, grain length, and plant height. Therefore, pedigree information can be useful in tracing genes of additive action. D^2 estimates based on quantitative trait differences between parents were significantly associated with F_1 performance for plant height and midparent heterosis for total plant weight, plant yield, and 100-grain weight.

Table 1. Correlation coefficients among genetic diversity measures in maintainer (B) and restorer (R) lines of rice.^a

	Quantitative trait	SSR
Pedigree record	-0.061 (B) 0.216**(R)	0.092* (B) 0.033 (R)
Quantitative trait		0.025 (B) 0.047 (R)

^a*, **indicate significance levels of $P \leq 5\%$ and 1% , respectively.

Table 2. Correlation between hybrid performance (F_1), midparent heterosis (H_{MP}), and different diversity measures of parental lines.^a

Basis for diversity	Plant height (cm)	Total plant weight (g)	Grain yield per plant (g)	100-grain weight (g)	Grain length (mm)	Grain width (mm)
SSR markers						
F_1	-0.03	-0.02	0.07	-0.04	-0.01	0.09
H_{MP}	0.30	-0.06	0.06	0.06	0.05	0.01
Pedigree record						
F_1	0.34*	0.19	-0.07	0.43**	0.43**	-0.26
H_{MP}	0.30	0.14	0.10	0.01	0.26	0.05
Quantitative traits						
F_1	0.40*	-0.03	-0.18	0.16	0.05	0.32
H_{MP}	0.12	0.38*	0.40*	0.42*	0.23	0.01

^a*, **indicate significance levels of $P \leq 5\%$ and 1% , respectively.

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Epistatic QTLs affecting hybrid breakdown in recombinant inbred populations derived from indica-japonica crosses

Z.K. Li, IRRI and Department of Soil and Crop Sciences, Texas A&M University, College Station, Texas 77843 USA; L.J. Luo, H.W. Mei, D.B. Zhong, C.S. Ying, China National Rice Research Institute (CNRRI), Hangzhou; Q.Y. Shu, D.L. Wang, Department of Agronomy, Zhejiang Agricultural University, Hangzhou, China; R. Tabien, J.W. Stansel, IRRI; and A.H. Paterson, Department of Soil and Crop Sciences, Texas A&M University, USA E-mail: Z.Li@cgiar.org

Inbreeding depression (ID), the depressive effect on the expression of traits, arises primarily from increasing homozygosity in outcrossing species. Heterosis (H), the superiority of F_1 performance relative to parental performance, is associated with heterozygosity (Allard 1960, Filho 1999). In quantitative genetic theory, ID and H are due to nonadditive gene actions and are considered as two aspects of the same phenomenon (Mather and Jinks 1982). Recently, Li et al (1997) suggested that hybrid breakdown (HB) in rice is part of ID due largely to additive epistasis. In this study, we examined HB in a recombinant inbred (RI) population of rice and mapped main-effect and epistatic quantitative trait loci (QTLs) associated with grain yield and

biomass, which appeared to shed some light on the genetic basis of HB in rice.

A set of 254 F_{10} recombinant inbred lines (RILs) derived from a cross between Lemont (japonica) and Teqing (indica) was used. The parents and RILs were evaluated for grain yield (GY) and biomass (BY) per plant in a replicated trial conducted at CNRRI in 1996. Genotyping was conducted at Texas A&M University, USA. A complete linkage map of 182 markers spanned 1,918.7 cM and covered 12 rice chromosomes with an average interval of 11.3 cM between markers (Li et al 1999). The values of HB (RILs - MP) for GY and BY were used as input data, where MP was the mid-parent value. A mixed linear model was used for mapping epistatic QTLs using

QTLMAPPER v. 1.0 based on a threshold of LOD >2.5 (Wang et al 1999).

The mean HB of the RILs was -2.7 t ha⁻¹ (-54.6%) and -3.7 t ha⁻¹ (-37.7%), ranging from -4.5 t ha⁻¹ (-90.8%) to 2.5 t ha⁻¹ (50.8%) for GY and from -7.6 t ha⁻¹ (-78.4%) to 4.1 t ha⁻¹ (42.2%) for BY.

The segregation of the RILs for BY and GY could be largely explained by four main-effect QTLs and seven pairs of epistatic loci (see table). Four main-effect QTLs affecting both GY and BY were mapped to chromosomes 2, 3, and 9, which unlikely contributed to HB since the effects of two alleles at each QTL tend to cancel each other. On the other hand, all but one pair of the epistatic QTLs had significant positive epistatic effects on GY